

ISic0046

I.Sicily inscription 0046

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.07.21 (on display)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found 16 October 1751 by Thomas Hollis in the area of the Vigna Cassia catacombs ('behind the hermitage of S. Maria di Gesù')

Coordinates

37.076278, 15.288184

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3547

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. (Χρίστο)ς

2. Κοββουλ

3. δέους

Apparatus

Text based on photograph

Translation

Commentary

Note that the palm and the chi-rho are upside down in relation to the text, and the chi-rho is in combination with a small lunate sigma. cf. Agnello, *Silloge*, n.67 = ISic1632 for another example of the Greek transliteration of the Latin form *Quodvultdeus*, known in the Latin form in Sicily of *Quddeusult* (e.g. CIL

10.8045.19). Thomas Hollis gave this particular text to the Sicilian antiquarian Torremuzza, who in turn gave it to Palermo museum

Digital identifiers:

TM 491682

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PHI 175713

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7175 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1970. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelia.* Palermo. At 47

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. *Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelika 6.* Palermo. At 113

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità. Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 342

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Photo J.Prag, courtesy Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas